

Techno-economic analysis of blue ammonia synthesis using cryogenic CO₂ capture Process-A Danish case investigation

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ABSTRACT

Ammonia is a vital chemical with numerous applications. Currently, the primary methods for generating the necessary reactants for ammonia production involve steam methane reforming (SMR) and cryogenic air separation unit (CASU), while the Haber-Bosch process converts these reactants into ammonia. However, the SMR process releases substantial amounts of CO₂, making it imperative to employ an efficient and cost-effective CO₂ capture technology to mitigate emissions. This investigation focuses on evaluating the cryogenic CO₂ capture (CCC) process for blue ammonia production and provides a thorough economic analysis, estimating both the initial investment costs and operational expenses involved in producing blue ammonia. The results indicated that the CCC process can capture 90% of the CO₂ content in the flue gas emitted by the SMR, incurring an energy penalty of 0.724 MJ_e/kg_{CO₂} while capturing CO₂ in the liquid phase with purities exceeding 99.9%. In this case, the estimated CO₂ capture costs would be 18.05, 45.1, and 16.65 USD/ton in 2021, 2022, and 2023, respectively. This represents a 40% reduction compared to the CO₂ capture costs associated with conventional amine-based technology. The results of this study indicate that the annual electricity costs for ammonia production increase by 38.5% and 64.2% when employing the CCC and amine-based processes, respectively. This investigation employed an isothermal reactor for ammonia synthesis, using the heat from the exothermic reaction in a water ammonia absorption refrigeration cycle (ARC) to condense and purify ammonia. The results show that the ARC system can effectively condense ammonia at -6 °C, producing a liquid ammonia stream with 99.3% purity. This leads to a 95% reduction in power consumption compared to a vapor compression refrigeration cycle (VCRC). Consequently, this method has the potential to decrease the annual operational costs for ammonia production by 2.92%, 2.69%, and 3.13% in 2021, 2022, and 2023, respectively. This study indicated that the hydrogen production unit incurs the highest initial investment costs, as well as operating costs, in the blue ammonia production process, followed by CASU and the Haber-Bosch process.

1. Introduction

Ammonia stands out as one of the most demanding industrial chemicals. According to statistics, around 146 million tons of ammonia were generated worldwide in 2019 [1]. Projections suggest that ammonia production will reach 1.2 billion tons by 2050. Ammonia finds its primary application in the agricultural sector, where over 85% of the produced ammonia is utilized as fertilizer [2]. Additionally, ammonia serves as a carbon-free fuel, offering a potential solution to substantially

mitigate CO₂ emissions and reach CO₂ neutrality by 2050. However, special techniques, such as combustion with alternative reactive fuels and implementing pre-cracking combustion are essential for enhancing the combustion properties of ammonia [3]. Ammonia finds extensive application as a refrigerant. In this instance, ammonia, acknowledged as a natural refrigerant, can serve as a substitute for HCFCs and HFCs refrigerants, known for their severe environmental impact [4]. Ammonia is also one of the best options for hydrogen storage and it is mostly due to its exceedingly high stability and hydrogen density [5]. According to

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Ref. [6], ammonia poses a lower fire hazard compared to other hydrogen energy carriers. However, it presents a relatively high health hazard as a hydrogen carrier.

So far, the dominant technology for ammonia production has been the Haber-Bosch process, satisfying over 96% of the ammonia requirements [7]. This technology operates at elevated temperatures (400–500 °C) and pressures (150–200 bar) and optimized over the past century [8,9]. Despite achieving a substantial 74% reduction in energy consumption through optimizations over the past century [10], the Haber-Bosch process remains highly energy-intensive, underscoring the need for novel methods to further mitigate its energy demands. Spatolisano et al. [11] proposed utilizing a phosphate solution for ammonia absorption and separation from unreacted gases as an alternative to employing chillers for ammonia condensation, aiming to reduce the power consumption of the Haber-Bosch process. Petukhov et al. [12] also explored replacing the traditional ammonia condensation unit with a membrane-assisted gas absorption system to separate the generated ammonia from unreacted gases. This initiative aimed to improve the energy efficiency of the Haber-Bosch process. The study's findings revealed that employing the optimal absorbent and gas separation membrane facilitated the separation of ammonia from unreacted gases with purities reaching up to 98.7 vol%. Kyriakou et al. [13] introduced an electrochemical Haber-Bosch process employing a protonic ceramic membrane reactor. This innovative method offers significantly higher energy efficiency compared to the conventional Haber-Bosch process, leading to a reduction in power consumption and CO₂ emissions by 75% and 50%, respectively. Yüzbaşıoğlu et al. [14] explored various methods to mitigate CO₂ emissions during ammonia production via the Haber-Bosch process. Their study highlights CO₂ capture technologies, electrochemical methods, and water electrolysis as potential approaches to decrease emissions in conventional Haber-Bosch process.

Ammonia production relies on hydrogen and nitrogen as the primary feedstock. The cryogenic air separation unit (ASU) currently meets over 90% of the global nitrogen requirements, primarily attributed to its exceptionally high capacity and purity of the products [15]. The cryogenic ASU, a well-established technology with a Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of 9 [16], condenses and separates gas components in atmospheric air at different temperatures, leading to the production of nitrogen and oxygen with high purities. Cheng et al. [17] suggested employing a single-column cryogenic ASU to decrease initial investment costs and enhance the power demand flexibility of the plant. While the oxygen recovery in this setup may be lower compared to a double-column cryogenic ASU, it requires 21% less compression in the primary air compressor. Zhou et al. [18] also introduced an innovative single-column atmospheric cryogenic ASU aimed at decreasing process energy consumption, enhancing efficiency, and cutting the operating costs. This setup harnesses a thermal pump—a nitrogen compressor that utilizes the latent thermal energy of the streams within the column. They demonstrated that this system could lower the cryogenic ASU power consumption by 23% while producing nitrogen and oxygen with purities meeting industrial standards. In addition to cryogenic ASU, pressure-swing adsorption (PSA) can successfully separate nitrogen from air. The PSA technology with TRL of 9, can utilize zeolites for nitrogen adsorption and separation [16]. In this case, the adsorption process takes place at high pressures, followed by desorption process at atmospheric pressure. Polymeric membranes can also generate the required nitrogen for ammonia synthesis with purities up to 99% [19]. Nevertheless, it has been demonstrated that this technology is better suited for oxygen generation with medium purities up to 40 vol% in small-scale plants with capacities ranging from 10 to 25 tons per day [20].

Various methods, such as coal gasification, water electrolysis, photolysis, solar thermochemical cycles, biophotolysis, and biomass conversion, are accessible and can efficiently generate hydrogen [21]. Nevertheless, steam methane reforming (SMR) currently provides over 95% of the global demand for hydrogen [22]. However, this approach relies on natural gas as a feedstock, contributing to the depletion of fossil

fuel resources. Additionally, this method has comparatively high CO₂ emissions. Katebah et al. [23] indicated that the production of 1 kg of hydrogen using SMR results in the emission of 8.47 kg of CO₂. Under this situation, it is crucial to employ post-combustion CO₂ capture technologies to mitigate the CO₂ emissions associated with SMR. Tarun et al. [24] utilized MEA absorption process as well as membranes to capture and separate CO₂ generated within the SMR process. The results indicated that CO₂ capture technologies can operate with lower energy penalties when the feed stream entering the reformer reactor has higher temperatures, while the inlet streams to water-gas shift reactors have lower temperatures. Shi et al. [25] also employed vacuum swing adsorption (VSA) to capture CO₂ from a SMR plant. In this investigation, they used silica gel as sorbent material to absorb and capture CO₂. The results indicated that the designed CO₂ capture system can capture 90% of CO₂ content in the tail gas with 95% purity. Collodi et al. [26] conducted a techno-economic analysis on MEA and MDEA CO₂ capture technologies when separating CO₂ from the flue gas emitted by SMR. The results indicated that the integration of CO₂ capture technologies with SMR could lead to an increase in the levelized cost of hydrogen generation, falling within the range of 2.1–5.1 c€/Nm³. The cryogenic CO₂ capture (CCC) process which belongs to Chart/Sustainable Energy Solutions Cryogenic Carbon Capture™ represents a novel CO₂ capture technology capable of efficiently capturing CO₂ from SMR. This technology is very energy efficient when compared with conventional amine-based methods. It can capture and separate CO₂ from a gas mixture with energy penalty ranging from 0.71 to 0.92 MJ_e/kgCO₂ [27]. This technology can capture CO₂ with exceedingly high purities (>99.9%) and rates [28]. Moreover, this technology is exceptionally cost-effective, boasting overall costs that are at least 30% lower than those associated with oxyfuel combustion or amine-based methods [29].

This investigation performs a techno-economic analysis of the blue ammonia production by integrating the SMR with the CCC process for the first time. This investigation considers the whole value chain of blue ammonia synthesis and estimates the initial investment costs for establishing the cryogenic ASU, SMR integrated with the CCC process as well as the Haber-Bosch process. Additionally, this investigation computes operating costs in these sectors by considering the electricity spot price and the price of natural gas for ammonia production at a rate of 1 kg/s. In this investigation, a water ammonia absorption refrigeration cycle (ARC) exploits the heat of ammonia synthesis reactor to provide the cooling for ammonia condensation. This compares the purity of yielded ammonia, initial investment costs, and operating costs associated with the utilization of a conventional vapor compression refrigeration cycle (VCRC), ARC, and a combination of these two systems (ARC-VCRC) for the condensation and purification of ammonia.

2. Methodology

This section describes the blue ammonia production process and outlines the kinetics used to model the process in Aspen Plus. The discussed production process has the capacity to generate 27.911 million tons of ammonia annually. To accomplish this, it necessitates an annual supply of 323 million tons of nitrogen from CASU and 4.994 million tons of hydrogen from the SMR process, resulting in an annual emission of 44.534 tons of CO₂.

2.1. Process description

Fig. 1 indicates the simplified process design for blue ammonia production. According to this figure, a pump pressurizes liquid water (state 1) to 26 bar (state 2). Subsequently, the outlet streams from reformer reactor (state 9) and HT-WGS reactor (state 11) preheat the pressurized water (states 3 and 4). In this case, a compressor elevates the pressure of natural gas (state 6) assumed in this investigation to be methane, to 26 bars (state 7). Despite the MSR reactor exhibiting superior performance at lower pressures and achieving increased

power consumption. Additionally, the CCC process evaluated in this study applies robust heat integration, which warms up all product streams to ambient temperature by cooling down the incoming streams. Although previous studies [30] have considered more energy-efficient compressors and blowers for the CCC process, this study assumed an isentropic efficiency of 0.87 for all compressors within the CCC process and other sub-units depicted in Fig. 1. This consideration ensures a fair comparison between the CCC and amine-based processes when utilized for blue ammonia production.

As illustrated in Fig. 1, a cryogenic air separation unit (CASU) produces the required nitrogen for ammonia production. This investigation, however, does not delve into optimizing the CASU; instead, it considers a simple two-column CASU capable of producing nitrogen with purities exceeding 99.99% [31]. Additionally, as illustrated in Ref. [31], maintaining an oxygen content in the feed stream of the ammonia synthesis reactor below 10 PPM is crucial to prevent catalyst poisoning. Consequently, the nitrogen stream produced by the CASU contains less than 8.6 PPM of oxygen. In this case, the feed stream of the ammonia synthesis reactor contains only 0.9 PPM of oxygen, thereby ensuring the prevention of catalyst poisoning with the use of the nitrogen stream generated by the CASU. This considers an air stream (state 67) which is devoid of humidity and pollutants, comprising 20.95 mol% oxygen, 78.1 mol% nitrogen, and 0.95 mol% argon. As illustrated in Fig. 1, a compressor pressurizes the air, increasing its pressure to 6 bar (state 68). Subsequently, a divider splits it into two streams. The major stream (state 70) enters a multi-stream heat exchanger, cooling to $-166\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (state 76), and then proceeds to the high-pressure column (HPC) operating at 5 bars. The second compressor further pressurizes the minor stream before entering the multi-stream heat exchanger. This stream cools to $-166\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (state 74), transitioning to a liquid phase by warming up the cold streams. It then expands through an expansion valve, lowering its temperature to $-191\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (state 75), before entering the low-pressure column (LPC) operating at 1.3 bar. Fig. 1 underscores the heat integration between the HPC and LPC, where the HPC condenser, responsible for condensing the rich nitrogen stream (state 77), provides heat for the LPC reboiler. A portion of the condensed stream (state 79) is recycled to the top of HPC, while the remaining portion (state 82) expands (state 83) before entering the LPC. The rich oxygen stream (state 80) exits the HPC in liquid form, experiencing expansion (state 81) before entering the LPC. The LPC generates pure nitrogen (state 89) in the gas phase, leaving the column's top and entering the multi-stream heat exchanger. The oxygen stream, with a purity exceeding 99.8 mol %, exits the flash tank's bottom in liquid form (state 87), entering the multi-stream heat exchanger. Alongside these product streams, a waste stream (state 88) exits the LPC, entering the multi-stream heat exchanger. Consequently, the waste stream, nitrogen stream, and oxygen stream warm up in the multi-stream heat exchanger by cooling the incoming air streams.

This investigation focuses on an isothermal reactor for ammonia synthesis, where the heat generated within the reactor, stemming from the exothermic reaction, drives the ARC process. As detailed in Refs. [32, 33], the primary application of the ARC lies in air conditioning systems, typically achieving a cooling effect of $2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ when ambient air at $30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ cools absorber. However, taking into consideration the Danish climate, cooling through ambient air or water at $15\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ can reliably cool the absorber, allowing the ARC to achieve lower temperatures. As illustrated in Fig. 1, a mixer combines the compressed blue hydrogen stream (state 66) from the SMR plant with the nitrogen stream from the CASU (state 95). The resulting stream (state 96) then combines with the recycled stream of unreacted gases (state 106) before entering the ammonia synthesis reactor, which operates at 150 bar and $450\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The output of the reactor (state 98) cools down by heating the recycled stream (state 105) before undergoing further cooling through water. Fig. 1 demonstrates the integration of ARC and VCRC systems for cooling and condensing the ammonia stream. In this configuration, the ARC initially cools the stream to $-6\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (state 101), followed by the

VCRC system further cooling it to $-19.3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (state 102). Expanding the ammonia stream through the expansion valve reduces its pressure to 133 bars before entering the flash tank (state 103). This expansion, occurring before the separation process in the flash tank, not only decreases the compression work required in the VCRC to cool the ammonia stream to $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ but also produces higher purities upon separating the condensed ammonia stream in the flash tank. The flash tank releases the condensed ammonia from the bottom (state 104), while a compressor pressurizes the unreacted gases (state 106) exiting from the top (state 105) before recycling them back to the reactor.

Table 1 presents the temperature, pressure, and composition of the key streams entering and exiting the subsystems depicted in Fig. 1.

2.2. Kinetic models

This section outlines the kinetic models employed to simulate the reformer and water gas-shift reactors for blue hydrogen production, along with those utilized for modeling ammonia production within the Haber-Bosch process.

2.2.1. Kinetic models for reformer and water gas-shift reactions

As previously mentioned, the reformer produces a fuel mixture primarily composed of H_2 and CO by introducing steam and CH_4 at elevated temperatures. This conversion takes place in the reformer through the reactions given by Equations (1)–(3) over nickel-based catalyst. It is worth noting that reaction 2 represents the water gas shift reaction which is a side reaction in the reformer.

One can model the steam methane reformer as well as water gas shift reactors using plug flow reactor models available in Aspen Plus. Hence, this investigation utilized the Langmuir Hinshelwood Hougen-Watson (LHHW) kinetic formulation to model the reactions given by Equations (1)–(3) using the rate expressions given as follows [35]:

$$r_1 = \frac{\frac{k_1}{P_{\text{H}_2}^{2.5}} \left(P_{\text{CH}_4} P_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - \frac{P_{\text{H}_2}^3 P_{\text{CO}}}{K_{\text{eq},1}} \right)}{(\text{DEN})^2} \quad (4)$$

$$r_2 = \frac{\frac{k_2}{P_{\text{H}_2}} \left(P_{\text{CO}} P_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - \frac{P_{\text{H}_2} P_{\text{CO}_2}}{K_{\text{eq},2}} \right)}{(\text{DEN})^2} \quad (5)$$

$$r_3 = \frac{\frac{k_3}{P_{\text{H}_2}^{2.5}} \left(P_{\text{CH}_4} P_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^2 - \frac{P_{\text{H}_2}^4 P_{\text{CO}_2}}{K_{\text{eq},3}} \right)}{(\text{DEN})^2} \quad (6)$$

where r_i , k_i , and $K_{\text{eq},i}$ ($i = 1, 2, 3$) represent the reaction rates for reactions 1, 2, and 3 in unit of $\text{kmol.kg}_{\text{catalyst}}^{-1}.\text{s}^{-1}$, the rate constant and equilibrium constants, respectively, while DEN denotes the adsorption expression given as follows:

$$\text{DEN} = 1 + K_{\text{CO}} P_{\text{CO}} + K_{\text{H}_2} P_{\text{H}_2} + K_{\text{CH}_4} P_{\text{CH}_4} + \frac{K_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} P_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}{P_{\text{H}_2}} \quad (7)$$

where K_j ($j = \text{CO}, \text{H}_2, \text{CH}_4, \text{and } \text{H}_2\text{O}$) denotes the adsorption constants. The values for the adsorption constant, as well as the rate constants and equilibrium constants used in Equations (4)–(7), are available in Ref. [36].

2.2.2. Kinetic models for ammonia production

This investigation models the ammonia synthesis over Haldor Topsøe

Table 1
Temperature, pressure, and composition of key streams shown in Fig. 1.

Stream number in Fig. 1	1	6	16	28	35	60	66	67	92	95	96	104
Temperature (°C)	15	15	25	17	15	28.6	286	15	17	897	449.71	-20
Pressure (atm)	1	1.974	23	1.25	1	108.6	148.04	1	29.6	148.04	148.04	131.261
Mole flow (kmol/hr)	300	100	455.14	565.19	358.27	5125.05	319.13	192.32	20.34	105.97	425.1	211.972
Composition (mol%)												
N ₂	0	0	0	66.01	83.3	0.038	0	78.1	1.96E-06	99.993	24.9	0.1
O ₂	0	0	0	1.5	1.89	3.78E-3	0	20.95	99.829	7.51E-4	1.87E-04	6.36E-6
CO ₂	0	0	19.25	0.23	2.9	99.94	0	0	0	0	0	99.6
CO	0	0	0.29	0.237	0.44	3.74E-4	0	0	0	0	0	0
CH ₄	0	100	2.42	1.948	2.45	0.013	0	0	0	0	0	0
H ₂	0	0	77.9	6.27	7.9	5.51E-4	100	0	0	0	75.07	0.3
Ar	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.95	0.1708	5.98E-03	1.49E-03	1.28E-4
H ₂ O	100	0	0.126	1.018	1.09	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
NH ₃	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CL	0	0	0	0	5.15E-3	2.36E-7	0	0	0	0	0	0

iron based KM1 catalyst considering the exothermic reaction given by Equation (8).

In this case, Equation (8) provides the reaction rate for ammonia synthesis over the iron-based catalyst in the unit of $kmol_{NH_3}.m^{-3}.hr^{-1}$ as follows [37]:

$$r_{NH_3} = k_f \left(K_a^2 a_{N_2} \left(\frac{a_{H_2}^3}{a_{NH_3}^2} \right)^{0.5} - \left(\frac{a_{NH_3}^2}{a_{H_2}^3} \right)^{0.5} \right) \quad (9)$$

where k_f , K_a , and a_i ($i = N_2, H_2,$ and NH_3) represent the kinetic constant of the reverse reaction, equilibrium constant, and the activity of the components involved in the reaction. Reference [37] comprehensively describes the calculation of these parameters. This investigation models

Fig. 2. Composition of outlet stream from the reformer reactor operating at a pressure of 26 bars when (a) S/C = 3 (b) S/C = 2.5 (c) S/C = 2.

the ammonia synthesis reactor considering the isothermal operating conditions, with the intention of harnessing the generated heat within the ARC system. Hence, like the reformer and WGS reactors, this investigation employed a plug flow reactor using the LHHW kinetic model to simulate the ammonia synthesis reactor.

3. Results and discussion

This section discusses the model results of the blue ammonia production process shown by Fig. 1. As previously mentioned, the reformer reactor demonstrates improved performance at lower pressures. Nevertheless, owing to the high pressure demands within the PSA unit located downstream of the reformer reactor, it is necessary to operate the reformer reactor at elevated pressure. Therefore, this reactor operates at a pressure of 26 bars. Fig. 2 illustrates the impact of temperature on the conversion of methane and steam into hydrogen in the reformer reactor for different steam-to-CH₄ ratios (S/C) while operating at a pressure of 26 bar. According to this figure, the composition of the outlet stream from the reformer reactor varies slightly with different S/C ratios. However, as depicted in Fig. 3, the rate of hydrogen production increases more noticeably when the S/C ratio is 3, as highlighted in reference [38]. Hence, this study selected an S/C ratio of 3 to achieve the maximum hydrogen yield. Additionally, Fig. 2 also indicates that the reformer reactor exhibits superior performance at higher temperatures, leading to its operation at 900 °C. Nevertheless, operating the reformer reactor at 900 °C leads to increased natural gas consumption, consequently emitting a substantial amount of CO₂. In this case, the hydrogen production unit emits 8.9 kg of CO₂ for every 1 kg of produced H₂. Therefore, the implementation of an efficient post-combustion CO₂ capture process is crucial for capturing and separating the CO₂. This investigation focuses on the CCC process to effectively capture and separate CO₂ from the flue gas resulting from the combustion of natural gas and hydrogen production within the MSR and WGS reactors.

Fig. 4 illustrates the power consumption and energy penalty associated with the CCC process when capturing 90–99% of the CO₂ content in the flue gas. It is worth noting that the energy penalty of CO₂ capture technologies is commonly evaluated in MJ per kilogram of captured CO₂, calculated by dividing the power consumption of the CO₂ capture technology in MW by the mass flow rate of captured CO₂ in kg/s. According to this figure, capturing CO₂ at higher rates results in an increase in power consumption within the process, thereby elevating the energy penalty associated with the CCC process. To illustrate, the CCC process requires lower temperatures when capturing the CO₂ content in the flue

Fig. 4. Power consumption and energy penalty of the CCC process for different CO₂ capture rates.

gas at higher rates. Consequently, the compression work within the cascade refrigeration cycle increases, leading to higher power consumption and an elevated energy penalty in the CCC process. According to Fig. 3, the power consumption and energy penalty in the CCC process exhibit a slight increase when raising the capture rate from 90 to 96%. However, the energy penalty experiences a substantial rise when capturing 99% of the CO₂ content in the flue gas. In this case, the cascade refrigeration cycle needs to cool down the CL to exceedingly low temperatures (<-130 °C). Hence, the CL can effectively cool the flue gas, causing the CO₂ content in the exceedingly diluted gas mixture to freeze at the top of the desublimation heat exchanger. This additional cooling for capturing 99% of the CO₂ content results in a significant upsurge in power consumption and the energy penalty of the CCC process.

It is worth noting that the existing point sources can simply integrate the CCC process as a retrofit technology, with its operation primarily dependent on electricity [28]. Therefore, calculating the operational expenses of the CCC process involves considering the electricity costs associated with the process. As a result, this investigation estimated the operational costs of the CCC process by considering the electricity spot prices in Denmark for the years 2021, 2022, and 2023 as provided in Ref. [39]. It is important to note that the blue ammonia production plant illustrated in Fig. 1 does not operate continuously throughout the year, requiring regular maintenance outages. Consequently, this investigation assumes an annual maintenance outage of six weeks for the plant. In this case, the main outage occurs over three weeks, spanning the last week of January and the first two weeks of February. Fig. 4 presents the CO₂ capture costs using the CCC process for capturing 90–99% of the CO₂ content in the flue gas for the years 2021, 2022, and 2023. Like Figs. 4 and 5 also shows a slight increase in the CO₂ capture costs as the capture rate rises from 90 to 96%, while one can observe a notable escalation when the capture rate increases from 96 to 99%. The high 2022 cost arise primarily from a sharp increase in the electricity spot price that year.

Biermann et al. [40] assessed the performance of the amine-based method when capturing and separating CO₂ from the flue gas generated by the SMR process. The amine-based method represents the most mature post-combustion CO₂ capture technology. They reported that the specific heat requirements in the stripper column vary within the range of 3.6–3.8 MJ/kgCO₂. Considering the lower bound as the specific heat duty of the reboiler and assuming that a heat pump with a coefficient of performance (COP) of 3 supplies the required heat for CO₂ desorption and solvent regeneration, the amine-process energy penalty would be 1.2 MJ_e/kgCO₂, significantly higher than the calculated energy penalty for the CCC process (i.e., 0.725 MJ_e/kgCO₂). Fig. 6 compares the CO₂

Fig. 3. The rate of hydrogen production in the reformer reactor as a function of temperature and S/C ratio.

Fig. 5. CO₂ capture costs for different CO₂ capture rates using the CCC process in 2021, 2022, and 2023.

capture costs when the CCC process and amine-based process capture 90% of the CO₂ content in the flue gas generated by the SMR process. According to this figure, the CO₂ capture costs of the CCC process are 60% of those for the amine-based process in 2021, 2022, and 2023.

As previously noted, the blue ammonia synthesis plant employs the Haber-Bosch process to convert hydrogen and nitrogen into ammonia, with the reactor operating at 450 °C and 150 bars. Fig. 7, provides a comparison between the outcomes of modeling the ammonia synthesis reactor in Aspen Plus and the experimental data supplied by Aparicio et al. [41], conducted at 450 °C and 214 bars.

This investigation investigates the feasibility of ARC, VCRC, and a hybrid system combining both (VCRC-ARC) for condensing and purifying the ammonia stream. It is crucial to highlight that the ARC system result in high energy efficiency and low power consumption compared to the VCRC system. Nevertheless, the ARC has limitations, unable to cool the ammonia stream below –6 °C or generate a liquid stream with 99.6% purity. On the other hand, the VCRC-ARC hybrid presents a promising solution for ammonia condensation and separation. It achieves lower temperatures, ensuring a 99.6% purity while simultaneously reducing the VCRC power consumption by 39%. However, economic analysis results using Aspen Plus Economic Analyzer (APEA) indicate

higher component costs for this system, as illustrated in Table 2.

Table 3 provides a comprehensive breakdown of electricity and natural gas consumption across various sub-units involved in blue ammonia production. These sub-units include CASU for nitrogen production, SMR combined with the CCC process for hydrogen production, and the ammonia synthesis unit, which converts reactants from CASU and SMR into ammonia while also condensing and purifying the ammonia stream. Based on the electricity spot price in Denmark and the costs of natural gas in Europe as provided in Ref. [42] one can calculate

Fig. 7. Validation of results for modelling the ammonia synthesis reactor.

Table 2

Comparison of ARC, VCRC, and VCRC-ARC for condensing and purifying the ammonia stream

Chiller type	Purification temperature (C)	NH ₃ purity (vol%)	Power consumption (kW)	Component costs (Million Euro)
ARC	–6	99.3	17.86	1.01
VCRC	–20	99.6	486.59	1.58
VCRC-ARC	–20	99.6	187	2.16

Fig. 6. CO₂ capture costs from the SMR plant when the CCC process and the amine-based method capture 90% of the CO₂ emissions.

Table 3

Summary of fuel and power consumption as well as annual operating costs for different operation units in the blue ammonia synthesis plant

Annual operating costs (M€)						
Unit operation		Power consumption (MW)	Natural gas consumption (SCM/day)	2021	2022	2023
CASU		1.213	–	0.8475	2.116	0.7813
SMR integrated with the CCC process		2.097	80757.25	16.197	44.259	13.863
Ammonia synthesis and purification	ARC	0.0345	–	0.0241	0.06	0.0222
	VCRC	0.771	–	0.538	1.345	0.4966
	VCRC-ARC	0.47	–	0.328	0.822	0.3027
Total	ARC	3.345	80757.25	17.0686	46.435	14.666
	VCRC	4.081	80757.25	17.5825	47.72	15.1409
	VCRC-ARC	3.78	80757.25	17.372	47.197	14.947

the annual operating costs of blue ammonia production in 2021, 2022, and 2023. As shown in Table 3, the SMR unit requires a considerable amount of natural gas, in addition to electricity, resulting in the highest annual operating costs compared to CASU and the ammonia production unit. Additionally, Table 3 illustrates the power consumption and operating costs of different technologies that can be utilized within the ammonia synthesis unit for condensing and purifying the ammonia stream. These technologies include ARC, VCRC, and hybrid ARC-VCRC. Based on the data shown in Table 3, opting for the ARC process over the VCRC method significantly reduces both total power consumption and total annual operating costs for blue ammonia production.

Fig. 8 illustrates the costs per ton of blue ammonia production for the years 2021, 2022, and 2023. The determination of these costs in this investigation relies on factors such as the electricity spot price, natural gas costs, and income generated from oxygen production in the CASU. The analysis considers the condensation and purification of ammonia carried out by ARC, VCRC, and VCRC-ARC. The oxygen produced in the CASU as a by-product which can generate income when producing blue ammonia. This study assumes that the generated oxygen can yield income at a rate of 1.3 USD/ kg_{O₂}, consistent with reference [43]. Fig. 7 also emphasizes that the costs associated with ammonia production reach their highest value in 2022 mostly due to an exceptionally high electricity spot price and elevated natural gas prices in that year. Furthermore, this figure highlights that the natural gas cost constitutes the largest share in the blue ammonia production costs. This is primarily due to the extensive use of natural gas, serving both as reactant and fuel to elevate the temperature of reactants to 900 °C and provide the required heat for the endothermic reaction occurring in the reformer reactor.

As previously mentioned, the CO₂ capture processes, particularly the CCC technology, rely exclusively on electricity when integrated with the SMR process for blue ammonia production. Consequently, these CO₂ capture processes contribute solely to the electricity costs associated with blue ammonia production. Fig. 9 compares the annual electricity costs for blue ammonia production using the CCC and amine-based processes. In this scenario, choosing the CCC process over amine-based methods results in a 19% reduction in annual electricity costs for blue ammonia production. This translates to savings of 0.503 million Euro, 1.256 million Euro, and 0.464 million Euro, based on electricity spot prices in 2021, 2022, and 2023, respectively.

Table 4 summarizes the outcomes of the economic analysis for the blue ammonia production process, employing the APEA tool in Aspen Plus to estimate the component costs of the process. It is noteworthy that this investigation estimated the cost of the iron-based catalyst and nickel-based catalyst at 0.18 USD/kg [44] and 100 USD/kg [45], respectively. Furthermore, utilizing the economic data provided by Ref. [46] and assuming a linear relationship between the capacity and the cost of the PSA unit, this investigation estimated the cost of the required PSA unit for hydrogen purification. Moreover, one can approximate the installed plant costs by multiplying the total equipment costs provided in Table 4 by a Lang factor of 4.7, as suggested in Ref. [47] for fluid processing plants.

Fig. 10 additionally illustrates the distribution of initial investment

costs among the sub-units. According to this figure, the SMR sub-unit, which has the highest initial investment costs, allocates the most significant portion towards the equipment costs. In contrast, the ammonia production and purification unit utilizing the VCR-ARC technology shows the smallest proportion of the equipment cost.

4. Conclusion

This investigation conducted a comprehensive techno-economic analysis of blue ammonia production, assessing the effectiveness of the CCC process in mitigating CO₂ emissions during hydrogen production using the SMR. The findings revealed that the energy penalty of the CCC process for this application varies in the range of 0.724–0.838 MJ_e/kg_{CO₂} when capturing 90–99% of the CO₂ emissions in the liquid phase. A simple comparison with conventional amine-based processes demonstrated a 40% reduction in CO₂ capture costs through the CCC utilization. This investigation utilized an isothermal reactor for the conversion of hydrogen and nitrogen into ammonia. The ARC system utilized the heat generated from the exothermic reaction to condense ammonia at –6 °C. Although this method cannot achieve purities exceeding 99.3%, it significantly cuts the power consumption by up to 95% compared to conventional VCRC systems. Furthermore, this condensation approach lowers the annual operation costs for ammonia production by 2.92%, 2.69%, and 3.13% in 2021, 2022, and 2023, respectively. This investigation further explored a hybrid chiller that integrates ARC and VCRC systems, leading to a 99.6% purity and a 39% reduction in power consumption compared to the VCRC system. Notably, the investigation highlighted that the SMR unit constitutes the costliest segment, accounting for 52.77% of initial investment costs.

The blue ammonia production method discussed in this study proves to be significantly advantageous compared to emerging methods like electrochemical-based processes and integrated reactors, which combine catalysts and sorbent materials for in-situ ammonia separation. In this case, employing the CCC and ARC-VCRC processes can substantially reduce the power consumption of the blue ammonia production process and enhance its overall energy efficiency. Despite its reliance on fossil fuel resources and higher power requirements compared to electrochemical-based methods and integrated reactors, it circumvents the challenges inherent in these alternatives and is scalable for large-scale applications. To illustrate, electrochemical methods are still at a very low Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of 1–2 [48], necessitating additional research and development to enhance Faradaic efficiency and achieve higher ammonia conversion rates [49]. Furthermore, the integrated reactor, with a TRL ranging from 1 to 5 [48], also encounters challenges, necessitating further research and development to identify promising sorbent materials capable of effectively separating ammonia at elevated temperatures.

The current investigation did not explore the influence of energy storage on the operational expenses of the CCC process. Consequently, one can develop a transient model in Aspen Plus to analyze how energy storage affects CO₂ capture costs when implementing the CCC process for blue ammonia production. This study did not consider the cost of CO₂ transportation and storage, as these factors strongly depend on the

Fig. 8. Ammonia production costs in (a) 2021 (b) 2022 (c) 2023 when VCRC, ARC, and VCRC-ARC condense and purify ammonia.

Fig. 9. Annual electricity costs in Euros for producing gray as well as blue ammonia, using both the CCC and amine-based processes. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Table 4

Summary of cost estimation for the components and complete plant of the blue ammonia production process shown by Fig. 1.

Equipment type	Costs (Million Euro)
Heat exchangers	3.872
Cooling towers	0.638
Distillation columns	1.93
Solid separator filter	0.018
Desiccant separator	0.24
Desublimation heat exchanger	0.157
Compressors and blowers	11.09
Furnace	1.2
Pumps	0.553
Flash tanks	0.635
Reactors	4.86
PSA	8.973 [46]
Total costs	34.166
Costs of establishing the plant	160.58

site where the SMR plant is located. Moreover, it is crucial to conduct a comprehensive comparison of both the initial investment costs and operational expenses between green ammonia production and blue ammonia production to assess the economic viability of green ammonia production.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Hossein Asgharian: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Larry Baxter:** Supervision, Software. **Florin Iov:** Supervision. **Xiaoti Cui:** Software. **Samuel Simon Araya:** Supervision. **Mads Pagh Nielsen:** Supervision. **Vincenzo Liso:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests Stephanie Burt is an employee of Chart Industries which owns the Cryogenic Carbon Capture™ process described in this paper and Larry Baxter, a professor at both Brigham Young and Aalborg University, is its inventor. Their roles in this paper involved helping set up the Aspen process simulation model. They had no role in evaluating or comparing the energy efficiencies, capital costs, or operating costs of the processes. All other authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Fig. 10. Distribution of the equipment costs for blue ammonia production. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

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